

BIOGAZ VA BIOO'G'IT ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA INDUKSION QIZDIRGICHLARDAN FOYDALANISH.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada biogaz va bioo'g'it ishlab chiqarish qurilmalarida induksion qizdirgichlarni qo'llab ularning ish unumdorligi hamda energiya samaradorlikka erishishning takliflari keltirilgan bo'lib bunda biogaz qurilmalarining zamonaviy usulda echimlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Induksiya, biogaz, bioo'g'it, induktor, metal, chastota, manbaa, yuqori chastota, Gers, qizdirish.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены предложения по достижению эффективности и энергоэффективности с использованием индукционных нагревателей в устройствах для производства биогаза и биоудобрений, а также представлены современные решения для биогазовых устройств.

Ключевые слова: Индукция, биогаз, биоудобрение, индуктор, металл, частота, источник, высокая частота, Герц, нагрев.

Abstract. In this article, proposals for achieving efficiency and energy efficiency using induction heaters in biogas and biofertilizer production devices are presented, and modern solutions for biogas devices are presented.

Key words: Induction, biogas, biofertilizer, inductor, metal, frequency, source, high frequency, Herz, heating.

Induksion qizitish tok o'tkazuvchan jismlarning elektromagnit maydonida uyurma toklarini induksiyalash hisobiga qizishidir.

Metallarni induksion qizitish ikki fizik qonunlar: Faradey-Maksvel elektromagnit induksiyasi qonuni va Joule-Lens qonunlariga asoslangan. Metall jismlar o'zgaruvchan magnit maydoniga oylashtiriladi va ularda uyurmali elektr maydoni xosil bo'ladi.

EYUK induksiyasi magnit maydonining o'zgarish tezligi bilan aniqlanadi:

$$e = -\partial\phi / \partial t$$

Bu bog'liqlik ifoda bilan ta'riflangan elektromagnit induksiyasi qonunining integral shakli hisoblanadi. Induksiya EYUK ta'sirida jismlarda uyurmali (jism ichida tutashadigan) tok oqishi natijasida Joule-Lens qonunga

asosan issiqlik ajraladi. Induksion qizitish bevosita va kontaktsizdir. U juda qiyin eriydigan metallar va qotishmalarni ham erita oladigan haroratga erishish imkonini beradi.

Jadal induksion qizitishga faqat yuqori kuchlanish va chastotali elektromagnit maydonda maxsus qurilma induktorlar yordamida erishiladi. Induktorlar 50 Hz chastotali tarmoqdan (sanoat chastotali uskunalar) yoki individual manbadan-generatorlar, o'rtta va yuqori chastota tok o'zgartirgichlaridan ta'minlanadi. Bilvosita past chastotali induksion qizitish uchun oddiy induktor sifatida metall truba ichiga joylashtirilgan yoki yuzasiga o'ralgan (tortilgan yoki spiral ko'rinishidagi) izolyasiyalangan simdan foydalanish mumkin. O'tkazgich sim induktordan tok o'tganda trubada qizituvchi uyurmali tok yuzaga keladi. Issiqlik trubadan qizitiladigan muhitga (suv, trubadan o'tadigan havo va hokazo) uzatiladi. Metallarni o'rtta va yuqori chastotada induksion bevosita qizitish keng tarqalgan. Buning uchun maxsus tayyorlangan induktorlardan foydalaniladi. Induktor o'zidan elektromagnit to'lqin chiqaradi, u qizitiladigan jismga tushib, unda so'nadi. Yutilgan to'lqinlar energiyasi jismda issiqlikka aylanadi. Ajraladigan elektromagnit to'lqinlar turi (tekis, silindr shaklidagi va hokazo) qizitiladigan jism shakliga qanchalik yaqin bo'lsa, qizitish samaradorligi yuqori bo'ladi. SHuning uchun tekis jismlarni qizitish uchun-tekis, silindr shaklidagilar uchun silindr ko'rinishidagi (solenoidli) induktorlardan foydalaniladi (1. b, v- rasm). Umumiy holatda ular elektromagnit energiyasini kerakli yo'nalishda jamlash uchun murakkab shaklga ega bo'lishlari mumkin.

1-rasm. Induktorlar: a-sanoat chastotali; b-tekis yuzalarni toblash uchun; v-silindr shaklidagi; 1-po'lat truba; 2-izolyasiyalovchi sim.

O'rtta va yuqori chastotali qizitish uskunalarining prinsipial elektr sxemasi 2-rasmda tasvirlangan. Kuchlanish manbaiga (UZ) tebranish konturi S-L ulangan bo'lib, unda kerakli chastotada so'nmaydigan tebranishlar xosil bo'ladi. Tebranish konturining induktivligi L sifatida yuqori chastotali pasaytiruvchi (moslashtiruvchi) transformatorning TV birlamchi chulg'ami xizmat qiladi, ikkilamchi chulg'am zanjiriga esa qizitiladigan jism joylashtirilgan induktor EK ulanadi. L ning qiymati transformator, induktor va jism parametrlari birgalikda xisobga olinib aniqlanadi.

Induktorlar odatda ko'ndalang kesimi yuzasi to'rburchak yoki aylana shaklidagi mis trubkadan tayyorlanadi, trubka ichidan sovutish uchun sovuq suv

oqadi.

2-rasm. Induksion qizitish uskunasiining prinsipial elektr sxemasi

Induksion qizitish po'lat maxsulotlar yuzasini toblash, plastik deformatsiyalashda (shtamplash, presslash va xokazo) to'la qizitish uchun metallarni eritish, termik ishlov berish, payvandlash eritib quyish, kavsharlash uchun qo'llaniladi: bilvosita qizitish texnologik uskunalarini (truba o'tkazgichlar va xokazo) isitish, suyuq muxitlarni qizitish, qoplamalarni, materiallarni, masalan, yog'ochni quritish uchun qo'llaniladi. Induksion qizitish uchun 50 Gs dan 5 Mgs gacha chastota qo'llaniladi. Induksion qizitish uskunalarini o'zida jarayonning (qizitishning) maqsadi (mexanik ishlov berish uchun to'la qizitish, yuzani toblash uchun qizitish va xokazo), jismning shakl va geometrik o'lchamlari, xarorat rejimi (to'la qizitish 1200...1300 °C gacha, yuzani toblash uchun -750 °C gacha) kabi ko'rsatkichlarni aks ettirgan texnik topshiriq asosida loyihalashtiriladi va tanlanadi. Topshiriqda qizitish vaqti τ yoki uskunaning unumdorligi m ko'rsatiladi. Agar bular ko'rsatilmasa, vaqt τ hisoblanadi. Uskunalarining asosiy parametrlari (quvvati, chastotasi, FIK, $\cos\varphi$) ishchi organ-induktorning issiqlik va elektr xisoblari asosida aniqlanadi. Eksploatatsiya sharoitlarida uskunalar vazifasi, chastotasi va generatorning tebranish quvvati bo'yicha tanlanadi. Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishida texnikalar remontida toblash uskunalarini, shuningdek suvni, binolarni, parniklarni qizituvchi past chastotali induksion qizitgichlari qo'llaniladi. Induksion qizitish uskunalarining asosiy parametri chastota. Xar bir isitish jarayoni uchun (yuzani toblash, to'la qizitish) chastotaning eng yaxshi texnologik va iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini ta'minlovchi maqbul diapozon mavjud. Yuzani toblash uchun qizitishda qo'llaniladigan chastotaga bog'liq bo'lgan induksion qizitishning ikki rejimi mavjud: chuqur va yuza. Chuqur qizitish (kichik chastotalarda) shunday chastotada f amalga oshiriladiki, bunda tokning kirib borish chuqurligi Δ toblanadigan qavat qalinligiga X_k taxminan teng yoki ko'proq bo'ladi. Qizitish bir yo'la qizitiladigan qavatning butun qalinligida X_k yuzaga keladi. Qizitishning bu rejimida tokning kirib borish chuqurligi nisbatan katta bo'lgani uchun $(\Delta q X_k)$, $\Delta \approx 503 \sqrt{\rho / (\mu f)}$ bog'liqlikka asosan chastota nisbatan past (kichik) bo'lishi kerak. Qizitish tez kechadi, yuqori FIK ega bo'ladi, lekin bu ta'minlash manbai quvvatining yuqori bo'lishini talab qiladi, shuning uchun bu usul keng ishlab chiqarishda qo'llanilishi maqsadga muvofiq. Yuzani qizitish (katta

chastotalarda) nisbatan yuqori chastotalarda, $\Delta < X_k$ da amalga oshiriladi. Xk chuqurlikgacha qizitish uzatuvchanlik xisobiga amalga oshadi. Ushbu rejim maxsulot ichkarisiga issiqlik o'tishi va tashqi muxitga tarqalishi xisobiga issiqlik isrofiga olib kelib, qizish vaqti oshadi, FIK pasayadi. Ta'minlash manbai kichik quvvatga mo'ljallangan bo'lsada energetik nuqtai nazaridan bu rejim afzal emas va uni unumdorligi uncha yuqori bo'lmagan uskunalarda qo'llaniladi.

Xulosa: Xulosa qilib aytganda biogaz va bioo'g'it ishlab chiqarishda qurilmani qizdirishda induksion qizdirish qurilmasidan foydalanish energiya tejash va maxsulotning samaradorligi hamda maxsulot sifatli bo'lishiga olib keladi.

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